

**FEINBERG'S CONTRIBUTION TO THE FIELD OF LITERATURE AND
EXAMPLES OF CREATIVITY****Qodirova Dilnoza Xoliq qizi**

Student of International Journalism faculty, UzSWLU

Email: dilnozaqodirova0623@gmail.com

Abstract: This article is approximately Alexander Feinberg, one of the foremost unmistakable and skilled writers of his time. Uzbekistan could be a affluent nation, where inventiveness, information, sympathy win, and which accepts that its children will develop up to be a concordantly created era, making a strong establishment for this. Alexander Feinberg, the proprietor of a awesome heart lived and worked in this favored arrive. The article examines the investigation of Feinbergs works, its part and importance in Uzbek writing. There are moreover brief portions frominterviews with the artist.

Key words: President, writing, interpreter, joy, noticeable, verse, imagination, meet, World War II, affluent, regard, one of a kind, geologist, nature, news coverage, privileged, multinational, cartoons, pilaf, competition.

INTRODUCTION. “Literature is the heart of the country, it reflects the most profound sense of being of the country. In todays complex world, it is vital to discover a way into the hearts of individuals, to utilize of the influential power of writing to direct them to respectable objectives. We are going make all the conditions for the ponder of hereditary legacy, the creation of incredible writing commendable of our great culture” –said President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev.

Alexander Feinbergs interesting works, which exemplify the most excellent conventions of classical verse and cherish for the arrive of Uzbekistan, are a special page within the history of our literature. The writer, whose childhood was went through within the troublesome a long time of World War II, was born in 1939 in Tashkent. After entering the Tashkent College of Geography, Feinberg traveled around the nation as a geologist and fell in adore with its wonderful and one of a kind nature. It was doing the period that his to begin with book, “The bike lane” was distributed. And through this, Alexander Feinberg started to rise to the positions of writing in Uzbekistan. He graduated from the news coverage workforce of the National College of Uzbekistan and has distributed more than a dozens of books of verse.

The most comes about and discoveries verse is as it were the field of the brave. Those who have fire in their hearts will drop on. Feinberg could be a gifted interpreter. He appeared perusers around the world that Uzbek specialists have great skills and experience. He made an awesome commitment to the distribution of Alisher Navoi's works in Russian. He moreover interpreted the leading cases of cutting edge Uzbek verse into Russian. At the same time, the artists works have been frequently deciphered into Uzbek, and he got to be a favorite writer of Uzbek perusers. The charm of his verse captivated people of all ages with distinctive personalities, views and states of mind. The poet translated into Russian ErkinVahidov's epic “Ruhlar isyoni” (Resistance of Spirits), lyrics by Abdulla Aripov, Omon Matchon, Sirojiddin Sayid, Khosiyat Rustamova. Feinbergs lyrics have been distributed in major distributors in Uzbekistan, Russia, Israel, and the Joined together States. Usually a distinctive case of the interdependency of cultures in human life and inventiveness. He isn't as it were the creator of

twelve collections of verse, but moreover a interpreter, who presented Russian-speaking perusers to the works of numerous extraordinary Uzbek artists, such as Abdulla Aripov, ErkinVahidov, JumaniyazJabbarov, RustamMusurman and others. He is the chairman of the yearly republican competition of youthful artists and referees youthful people who type in in Russian. He has composed seven screenplays, the foremost striking of which are “Under the blue sky”, “House under the hot Sun”, “Healed in Kandahar”. His screenplays have moreover been utilized to create four highlight movies and more than twenty cartoons. Feinbergs lyrics have a sparkof humor. Within the epic “Ruboiy tori” he depicted the constant pilaf of the Uzbek teahouse with chuckling in such a way that it is inconceivable to studied it without grin. Alexander Feinberg may be a member of the Writers' Union of Uzbekistan. For several years he chaired the Seminar of Youthful Journalists of Uzbekistan. In 2004, the artist was granted the Pushkin Decoration by the Proclaim of the President of Russia. The writer in his sonnet:

Each star contains a turn,
 Every dream and intention will be answered.
 The singing light meanders within the sky,
 Of course, each light sparkles in time.
 It rises and the ocean hops on the rock,
 I arrive on the shore the wind blows salt.
 As long as I live, the planetary lamp,
 Burn a star for me within the sky, -he composed.

Without a doubt, Alexander got to be one of the brightest stars within the sky of Uzbek verse. His works are profoundly established within the hearts of scholarly lovers.

CONCLUSION

In one of the interviews he was a address: -What can make you the most joyful or the unhappiest individual within the world? –For me, bliss on a worldwide scale –peace of our planet. As well as misery for millions of individuals is World War II. In my conclusion, it isn't right to request individual joy in a time when individuals are enduring. I need everybody to be cheerful. But it is incomprehensible... -he answered. Yes, he was such a kind man who wished peace and joy to all.Feinbergs commitment to the advancement of multinational Uzbek writing has been well-received by the government. The truth that he was granted the privileged titlesof “Honored specialist of culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan”, “Peoples writer of Uzbekistan” could be a verification of our boundless regard for this incredible man. The shinning memory of awesome artist, skilled interpreter, caring instructor Alexander Arkadevich Feinberg will stay in our hearts until the end of time.

REFERENCE:

1. Зиямухамедов, Д. Т. (2021). Вопросы передачи национального характера в переводах с китайского языка. тельность всем коллегам, принявшим участие в рецензировании статей сборника: МЮ Авдониной, СР Агабабян, ВМ Бухарову, ГМ Василь, 86.
2. <https://ziyouz.com>
3. <https://uz.m.wikipedia.org>
4. Pozilova, S., Rasulova, N., Khalilova, S., Aliyeva, N., &Rasulova, M. (2020). The role of creative education in the development of lifelong learning in an innovative society: Ways to organizing. *Journal of Critical Reviews*, 7(7), 379-383.
5. Mahbuba, R. (2022). THE ROLE OF STUDENT-STUDENT INTERACTION IN EFL CLASSROOMS. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(2), 63-66.